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Demographic Label Data in Wikipedia and Wikidata

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Contents

1	Abstract	3
2	Introduction	4
2.1	Data about People: Challenges of History and Ethics	5
2.1.1	Histories of managing data about the dead or the living, rights, and privacy	5
2.1.2	Gaps in the Record and Bias in Big Data	7
2.2	Demographic data in Wikidata	8
2.2.1	Background on Wikipedia	8
2.3	Demographic labeling	9
2.4	Labels in process	9
2.4.1	Demographic labeling by libraries	10
2.4.2	Demographic labeling by the US Census Bureau	11
2.4.3	Demographic labeling for advertising, business, media, and monetizing data	11
2.4.4	Demographic labeling in academia	12
2.4.5	Demographic labeling in the Wikimedia platform	13
3	Methods	13
3.1	Researching Aspects of Library Labeling: Name Authority Records with New Attributes: Gender	13
3.2	Exploration of Wikipedia and Wikidata	14
3.3	WikiProject Biography - Human Model	14
3.4	Wikidata queries to showcase data holdings	15
4	Results	15
4.1	Demographic labeling in Wikipedia articles	15
4.1.1	Wikipedia tracks its edits and offers a discussion forum on each page	16
4.2	Bots make data more accessible	16
4.3	Wikidata queries make public data even more accessible	17
4.4	PUT TANNER’S QUERIES HERE	18
5	Discussion	18
5.1	Demographic labeling in the Wikimedia platform	18
5.1.1	The nature of the platform includes applying labels	18
5.1.2	Accelerating rate of transfer between prose and datasets	18
5.2	Wikipedia’s established discourse on demographic labels	19
5.2.1	Individual Preferences	19
5.2.2	Due weight	20

5.2.3	Sorting into categories is given particular ethical consideration	20
5.3	Support and opposition for demographic labeling	21
5.3.1	Should we do it, just because we can?	21
5.3.2	Reasons for support	22
5.3.3	Reasons against	22
5.4	Directions for further exploration	22
6	Conclusions	22
7	References	23

1 Abstract

Wikipedia's community of editors develop and publish large numbers of biographies. Biographies include demographic data such as gender, nationality, and more. Examined individually, one may readily compare Wikipedia's biographies to biographies in any other publication. Examined collectively, the sum of Wikipedia's biographies take on new surprising characteristics.

Here we examine the demographic label data in Wikipedia and its structured data complement, Wikidata. We describe processes for producing or acquiring this data, and also demonstrate how users may export this data from the platform for reuse elsewhere. We review who else collects and redistributes similar data, what social and ethical processes they have in doing so, and how Wikipedia's values compare to those of other collections. We present reasons for speculating that Wikipedia's demographic data collections have an affect the broader media environment.

Wikipedia's community of editors collectively produce and curate this content. Producing biographies is a popular and encouraged activity among this editorial community.

Discussions about Wikipedia biographies to date however, Wikipedia and the connected Wikimedia ecosystem including Wikidata raise new social and ethical issues in demographic label data because of the way in which editors produce the data, the large scale of Wikipedia content and influence, and the ease with which data migrates from Wikipedia into the broader media environment. How does demographic labeling occur on Wikimedia platforms? What discussions surround its practice? Ethical guidelines for representation of individuals meet incompatible values: 1) additional specific data is more true to the individual, less reductive; 2) additional data is likely to be more intrusive, especially in sensitive areas a violation of the right to privacy. In light of the ready access to personal data of all kinds today, this paper examines and interprets the implications of third-party assignment of identity attributes such as gender and race in Wikipedia and Wikidata to human beings. In the history of recognition, the biographical records in printed antecedents to Wikipedia have always been biased toward elite men and certain occupations or standards of notability. Wikipedia's guidelines and Wikidata's functions can have unintended repercussions against diversity, equity, and inclusion. We describe both the mechanics of labeling and the ethical considerations brought into play, with a glance at the history of systemic identification for such purposes as claiming or withholding civil rights. Through case studies of pages on Wikipedia that feature crucial discussions on the ethics of demographic labeling, we show that Wikipedia editors take into consideration particular standards surrounding privacy and individual preference when choosing to apply demographic labels. We also cover the transfer of demographic information between Wikipedia and Wikidata, particularly significant because of the way the latter site can be queried for potentially sensitive information. Is it better to add more identifying attributes as accessible in published documents, perhaps recognizing more marginalized people and their communities, or is labeling an "outing" action by third parties, potentially harmful to the person, while it reinforces terms of difference that support inequality?

2 Introduction

"Demographic data labeling" is the process of assigning demographic data to a biographical profile. The community of editors in Wikipedia, Wikidata, and other parts of the Wikimedia ecosystem assign this data to the subjects of biographies through various processes. How does demographic labeling occur on Wikimedia platforms? To what extent does this assignment of data in Wikimedia platforms influence or affect the broader media environment? Ethical guidelines for fairly representing individuals run into incompatible principles: 1) additional specific data is more true to the individual, less reductive; 2) additional data is likely to be more intrusive, and may violate privacy. The scale and impact of demographic data can be measured better than ever with the rise of Wikipedia, a publication and online platform which has developed a culture and community of practice to advance that culture.[1] Wikipedia's content offerings include the publication of biographies,[2] which record demographic data such as occupation, race, nationality, or gender. In light of the ready access to personal data of all kinds today, this paper examines and interprets the implications of third-party assignment of identity attributes such as gender and race, primarily in examining Wikipedia and Wikidata. Most simply, Wikidata (the database "behind" the Wikipedia articles) has an extremely low threshold of privacy, and avidly pursues all structured data available to its bots and researchers. Wikipedia articles are more selectively edited and seek balance and respect for living persons. We speculate that a possible outcome of Wikimedia and related collection of demographic data would be near-universal access to demographic profiles for all documented individuals and groups. Just because we can do it, does it mean that we should?

Few people assume today that there can ever be such a thing as an objective and complete accounting of facts about all people in the world. Yet at the scale of data proliferating on the Internet in recent decades, the encyclopedic dream of modern societies seems almost realized: centralized, ready searching of information about people linked to authoritative sources. Wikipedia is an online answer to the demand for "a digest of knowledge" outstripping print encyclopedias in being potentially global and constantly up to date [3], 30. Its open sourcing from non-experts, among other policies, have intensified the doubts about authority (or warranted consensus of knowledge) that always plague reference works, according to Thomas Leitch. The bias of encyclopedias and biographical collections of previous centuries can be glaring to researchers looking back today. Perhaps because of the community of Wikimedians who conscientiously share their reasoning, and the capacity for comprehensive collation of systematic data from reliable databases, academic researchers increasingly respect and contribute to Wikipedia and study its practices and impact. We want to develop a clear picture of person-related data in Wikipedia and Wikidata within an historical and ethical perspective, showing the results of our queries and drawing on a wide range of examples and sources. Again, the opposing principles: It is good to add more kinds of information to a profile to approach the true complexity of a person or social category, aiding intersectional understanding, and some types or roles gain recognition that was denied in the past. It is good to bar, remove, or protect sensitive personal information to serve the right to privacy. In determining whether demographic data should be shared or restricted, we need to ask: Who (or what, in the case of bots) is gathering the human-related information? Why or according to what criteria is that information collected and how is it used? Are our general profiles of groups derived from biased and incomplete datasets? What are the possible effects on individuals or communities when we combine, share, and reuse various categories of personal information, even what is already made public for different purposes? These are questions to be raised not only about Artificial Intelligence (AI or machine learning), surveillance technologies, and biomedical ethics, but also of biographical collections of personal data. In this article, we describe Wikipedia's demographic practices, compare those to practices in other eras and arenas, present model datasets from Wikidata for discussion, and examine ethical and social issues that arise in third-party determination and use of personal data.[4]

Applications within the technological movement called "Web 2.0" or "participatory web" invite user engagement with countless consequences that may be positive, negative, or not yet understood.[5]

Wikipedia, now over twenty-one years old and proliferating in many languages as a prevailing reference encyclopedia, features in debates about many Web 2.0 platforms and practices[6] [1] [3] 58-70. Wikidata is a structured data complement to Wikipedia established in 2013.[7] One of the first things to emphasize is the free and public dissemination of everything in Wikipedia. Just as Wikipedia presents biographies, Wikidata presents biographic data records of people.[8] There are Wikidata records matched to every Wikipedia article, and additionally, Wikidata has records for many other concepts mirrored from other databases.[9] Offensive or harmful statements can be edited out of a Wikipedia article, but the distributed forces that are aggregating semantic interconnections (RDF) in tables in Wikidata may outsmart the considerations of ethical review on the more public-facing end of these endeavors.

A community of volunteer editors governs and sets policy for the Wikimedia platform, including Wikipedia and Wikidata.[1] This policy sets a criterion for inclusion referred to as "notability." [1][9] In contrast with social media or self-contributed "bios" of living persons (*Who's Who* in the era of print), or corporate or civic promotions or advertisements, a "notable" Wikipedia page requires "significant sources independent of the subject," and is likely to surface in other online references as well as the vast tabular web of recognition, Wikidata.[10] Many objections to Web 2.0 might generally be characterized as expressing alarm that amateurs have seized control of knowledge.[? ?] Paradoxically, Wikipedia, in its principles of neutral point of view, no original research, as well as notability, deflects responsibility for historical bias to a sort of polling of the available sources [? ?]. Commentators have remarked on the subset of Wikipedia that is its collection of biographies, often pointing to its disproportionate exclusion of women and marginalized people.[2][11]

The questioning of identity labels is a huge step forward in ethics, all things being equal. Many things are **not** equal, of course. History has never witnessed social equality—openness to every person regardless of race, gender, religion, economic status, or other systems of difference. Equity, the need to give equal opportunity at least, requires that we participate in the questionable practice of sorting and labeling people by the very kinds of identification that we wish to disregard in order to avoid discrimination. Such labeling, sorting individuals by group attributes—Muslim gardeners, Nicaraguan philosophers or what have you—is a process of recognizing shared identities and simultaneously discounting how each individual differs. Innocuous and helpful identification participates in the practices that can invade privacy and can be used for random or state-organized action against the individual.

The ethics of demographic labeling should be understood within a widespread crisis in recognition. We attempt here to think clearly about a practical challenge faced when researchers and their funders and institutions wish to help rather than harm the populations so recorded. We note a strong inflection at the point between life and death: data about the living are incalculably more sensitive than data about the dead, especially after a lapse of 70-100 years. Researchers strive to honor the wishes of the person if known, believing in the right to privacy as well as the unknowable uniqueness and uniqueness and fragility of each person. Apparently innocuous metadata or data-based algorithms can compound discrimination. At the same time, information specialists as well as activists insist on the value of respectful identity labels. This team has been looking closely at the state of practice and debate on these matters.

2.1 Data about People: Challenges of History and Ethics

2.1.1 Histories of managing data about the dead or the living, rights, and privacy

The long history of demography, or the study of populations, offers some perspective on the fraught issues surrounding personal data in the age of the Internet. The demand for statistical data about categories of individuals intensified during the rise of modern bureaucracies and nation-states, after the spread of printing. Wikipedia is associated not only with the spread of Web 2.0 but also with the history of print encyclopedias. Data collection about people can be a powerful political influence, as suggested by the association of high-impact encyclopedias of the Enlightenment with revolutions in the U.S., France, and eventually Germany, Italy, Russia, and Latin America. Shared

knowledge seems to entail shared power, and to dispel the authority of state religion and monarchy. The accumulation of data, however, can be motivated by centralized control and can capitalize on the information without the individual's consent. The discourse of individual rights has been associated with the meanings of privacy. The research field of demography emerged more recently to focus on these systems of wielding records about peoples, with norms and typical applications that change with the advent of new technologies.[12] Standards of scientific data collection have evolved with different aims and means, alongside changing expectations for published written lives about individuals. As Jacqueline Wernimont has noted in *Numbered Lives*, data collection in early eras was often associated with epidemics, displacements of populations due to war, famine, or economic disruption, and even the rise of colonialism and slavery. In the print era, civil rights became closely tied to literacy, and the emergence of widely-read personal narratives such as novels and biographies that specify the everyday experience of a few subjects not likely to be chronicled in national histories. Recognition, in other words, shifted from kings and heroes to the middle classes and women. Printed nonfiction narratives beyond reference works gradually began to favor more mixed characterization based on documentary evidence rather than idealized summaries of lives. By the nineteenth century, readers were more interested in “warts and all” portrayal of a quirky person who had marital difficulties and indigestion, overcame prejudices, and yet wrote important tomes. Invading a person's private life was always controversial but the claim to have a unique private life was a byproduct of modernization, intensified with new forms of data and publication.[?] By the turn of the twentieth century, there was a broad shift toward the public's right to know. Media and respected biographies alike are expected to bring celebrities down to human scale, revealing their misdeeds and struggles. Archives are now full of private correspondence, diaries, and documents that would in an earlier era have been burned upon the person's death by a protective relative or friend. Influenced by psychoanalytic approaches, the characters of the dead are subject to exposure and dissection. This in turn has an impact on archives and reference works, which in turn shape Wikipedia.

If biographical references and biographies document intimate details of the dead, what about the concerns about fair representation of the living? Privacy and security in shared records, whether archival or in printed or online sources, continue to be intense concerns for the living and their immediate families, perhaps all the more when everyone potentially can share daily life on social media. Some writers have regarded the Internet and social media as affording new forms of life writing that support self-affirmation and community, albeit mediated and at some levels exploited by the platform.[?]¹ Beyond engaging in social media, users are accustomed to submitting personal data with many everyday transactions, to the extent that governments or corporations might reach unlimited powers of surveillance [?]. But well before the rise of Facebook, many modern social benefits have depended on required or volunteered information about oneself, from the census to job applications, from birth certificates to immunizations for school enrollment. Lack of such documentation or the presence of certain identification can be wielded as a weapon against populations such as religious minorities, immigrants, or refugees.² A range of laws seek to protect individuals from unwarranted use of personal information or profiling. Human resources are guided by labor laws and EOEC guidelines to approach fair practices in hiring. The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) broadly outlaws the release of an individual's medical information by most health care providers and health plans.³ In a similar vein, institutions conducting research often use institutional review boards (IRBs) to ensure the confidentiality of individuals involved in studies.⁴ Dividing survey or medical study results from identifying data is standard practice, suggesting *less* personal data is more just.

¹The idea of anonymity online in early years suggested a workaround for race or gender bias (see Nakamura; Gray, both in Poletti and Rak

²Cultures at different periods have widely varied customs and rules for naming and documenting different milestones of life, as well as limits of sharing such personal information.

³“Your Rights Under HIPAA.” U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. HHS.gov. 19 January 2022. Accessed 14 April 2022. <https://www.hhs.gov/hipaa/for-individuals/guidance-materials-for-consumers/index.html>

⁴“Privacy and Confidentiality.” University of California, Irvine Office of Research. 2021. Accessed 14 April 2022. <https://services-web.research.uci.edu/compliance/human-research-protections/researchers/privacy-and-confidentiality.html>

2.1.2 Gaps in the Record and Bias in Big Data

But what about the data that is never counted or interpreted, or that is distorted by available fields or terms of data collection? In encyclopedic sources like Wikipedia and in many print publications, the production team (authors, editors, publishers) may intentionally write fact-based short or longer profiles about notable members of a particular demographic community. Like other source-based aggregation of authoritative information, it encounters the dilemma of benefiting from traditional ways to organize knowledge or adapting to new technologies and claims for reparation or more adequate recognition. Digital research has increasingly sought large-scale systematic comparison of vital information about historic individuals in sets, adapting the methods of prosopography or personography.⁵ Orlando, a project endeavoring to provide extensively detailed information about all British women writers, developed metadata to indicate whether a person self-identified as a member of a religion or not.[?]⁶ Alison Booth, in *How to Make It as a Woman* and *Collective Biographies of Women*, considers a history of such selective tradition-building through collections of chapter-length biographies. As Catherine D'Ignazio and Lauren Klein insist, "numbers...cannot speak for themselves" because data about humans are always derived from different "collection incentives" based on power [? ?] As we trend towards the condition of having global, inter-operable data about individuals and social identities, at least at the scale of Wikidata, we want to remain aware of the most advanced critiques of differences based on gender, race, disability, nationality, and economic status or occupation. In *Data Feminism*, D'Ignazio and Klein interpret the many dimensions of constantly labeling babies in the binary of boy/girl. They note that nonbinary people constantly face the difficulty of choosing the box to check on website forms, and add, "what is not counted...becomes invisible" (97). Diversifying the labels of choice seems like a way to affirm individuality, but ironically it can make the labels seem more essential (inborn) and generalized (*all females born in 1942 in Chicago must be alike*). Demographic labeling can resemble profiling in the policing sense, and can raise similar ethical concerns to DNA testing and face-recognition surveillance. It may generally seem the better option to add terms for distinct attributes to more accurately represent individuals, but creating subcategories within an identity attribute term can serve discriminatory purposes. For example, the statement of a white-supremacist mass shooter in Buffalo cited research by British researcher Michael Woodley arguing that "human beings can be scientifically divided into subspecies," a racist theory "widely rejected by contemporary mainstream academics" [?] Genetic research has shown the overwhelming biological kinship among all human beings: "race is not an inherent property of a person but a 'social fact' about their political place and social location" falsely attributed to phenotype; thus, "racial statistics do not reflect a stable 'ground truth,'" [?]. When researchers seek to redress a misrepresentation about a set of people, they encounter the gaps in archives due to systemic if unaware bias in defining what is recorded and how it is interpreted.⁷ Reference works have always answered to a consensus about persons who were notable in a national or international arena, and thus overwhelmingly cite male elites, a circularity of citing the already-cited. Such bias can build up over time even among proponents of causes for equality, for example between phases of studies in women, gender and sexuality. Michelle Schwartz and Constance Crompton, archivists of lesbian movements, follow Becki Ross in identifying a "generational rift" as 1990s activists stereotyped and dismissed their 1970s predecessors. Schwartz and Crompton urge "history-making" efforts of "preservation and transmission" as acts of "self-definition that resist[]the erasure of women's history by mainstream culture"; "lesbian researchers" should become "heirs to the history that they create." [13] 131 Archives are never neutral or exhaustive, but entail networks of agents who work within available information systems. Any agency or group endeavoring to serve diversity, equity, and inclusion, or to document bias in hiring or peer review, faces both gaps in the available data and misleading statistics derived from decontextualized and

⁵See Alison Hedley and Lorraine Janzen Kooistra 164-65 on Julia Flander's definition of personography as "the management of the identity of individual people" in Losh and Wernimont

⁶Being born into a Catholic family, educated Catholic, professing and continuing to be identified as a Catholic are all part of a biographical complexity seldom traceable in databases and Internet searches, but attempted in the scrupulous Orlando.

⁷Hughes-Watkins traces a twenty-first-century shift as librarians sought to redress "subjugation"; they still strive to respond to the charges brought by Howard Zinn as early as 1970, that the powerful determine what is collected and available to the public (2).

aggregated data. So many categories of human activity are discounted or overlooked. Algorithms can compound the bias in selective data, as recent scholarship has demonstrated, from Safiya Noble in *Algorithms of Oppression* to Shoshana Zuboff in *Surveillance Capitalism*. Many studies of machine learning show the effects of automated identification (as in, this is a picture of a woman) that then promote associations with gender-typical products; the well-known corporate incentives to monetize personal data for targeted advertising and other predictive control[?]. Corbett-Davis and Goel point out the inadequacies of various attempts to impose criteria of “fairness” in algorithms that deal with people. Efforts to mitigate unfairness, such as anti-classification, classification parity, and calibration of the algorithms are all “statistically limited” and may even serve to entrench racial biases that they seek to reverse. They advocate, instead, for informing algorithms with a consideration of “risk,” broadly defined, so that people who associated with risky attributes are treated similarly, whatever their other demographic traits might be.⁸

2.2 Demographic data in Wikidata

Key points for the context of this discussion are the Wikimedia platform is very popular among readers; it has a large and engaged Wikimedia community of contributors; the values-based "Wikimedia Movement" motivates the Wikimedia community to seek growth of diversity, open copyright licensing, and FAIR media; and Wikimedia content leaves the platform through Internet communication channels to circulate in other media environments.

2.2.1 Background on Wikipedia

Many commentators have told stories about Wikipedia. Some of those common talking points are not relevant for this discussion, but because Wikipedia is frequently misunderstood, a summary review is helpful.

Wikipedia was established in 2001 as a general reference encyclopedia. In 2004 founder Jimbo Wales stated the project’s vision as, "Imagine a world in which every single person on the planet is given free access to the sum of all human knowledge. That’s what we’re doing." <https://slashdot.org/story/04/founder-jimmy-wales-responds>

From its inception the project allowed anyone to edit any media. Unlike traditional reference works focused on a single nation or the metropolitan centers of power. It has never attempted complete representation of all people, living or dead, but it begins to approach further than any other source a global database of notable people. Wikipedia’s biographies, interlinked to entries on many entities, have included demographic information about individuals in ways that resemble conventional, always requiring citation of public documents rather than promotion or hearsay (a person who never makes it into news or printed sources will not receive a “page”). In 2012, the Wikimedia platform established Wikidata as a complementary platform to both convert Wikipedia’s information into structured data and also collect new general reference datasets to provide information of broad interest.[14]

After years of growth into nearly 400 languages, the scale and accessibility of Wikipedia and Wikidata content gives it a new nature and offers new use cases. Although Wikidata has significant gaps in information, the platform may be trending toward the establishment of bibliographic data profiles on all public figures across the globe. Increasingly, users can query any search term for a category of public figures to find structured demographic information on it and all its individuals. The ability to make such demographic queries has and will continue to raise social and ethical issues both within and outside of the Wiki community. Various voices within Wikidata have argued for indexing every human who has met the notability criterion. Pointing to documentation is challenging, but this indexing may include everyone who has ever been credited as author or featured as a subject of any published work. The potentially global scale of these matters is daunting, so we present model cases: when is Wikidata’s demographic profiling extensive but seemingly acceptable; when does it

⁸sources are in Zotero

raise social and ethical issues; and what are the implications of the practical case of demographic profiling of university researchers?

"The free encyclopedia that anyone can edit," as the homepage leader puts it, can facilitate synthetic cross-referencing among such collected datasets. Wikimedia community editors apply labels to people for a number of reasons, including that specifics of personal data arise in biographical sources, which indicate a name, a gendered pronoun, usually a place and date of birth or death and some pretext for notability such as an occupational achievement. For centuries, varied precedents for Wikipedia strove to correct the omissions of mainstream reference works and bring the biographical records of marginal groups to the center of attention[? ?] Wikimedia community projects which apply demographic labels to people include Art+Feminism, Women in Red, AfroCROWD, Wikimedia LGBT+, and professional organizations which create biographies by occupation. In addition, regional or language-based Wikimedia versions and pages for various countries create biographies by nationality.

Wikidata editors maintain various sorting processes for organizing Wikidata "properties", which are classifiers for Wikidata "items". One of those properties is "living people protection class (P8274)".[15] Querying Wikidata for use of this property can generate a list of items said to be problematic and a count of how often they are used.[16] We present a select list of some of these in Table 1.

Wikidata property label	identifier	count of uses
occupation	P106	9,199,128
sex or gender	P21	7,824,130
date of birth	P569	5,559,654
place of birth	P19	3,016,714
educated at	P69	2,257,168
employer	P108	1,608,919

Table 1. Wikidata properties that may violate privacy (partial). The Wikidata community maintains a list of its own properties which, when applied to the biographical profiles, may violate privacy. The count of uses changes continuously and reported here is a snapshot from June 2022.

2.3 Demographic labeling

Wikidata is a general reference resource which invites anyone to publish and share data of broad interest. As shown in Figure 1 Wikidata is a hub into which anyone may share data, where Wikidata will redistribute it to its existing user base.

2.4 Labels in process

Practitioners become aware of the instability of almost all terms that are confidently used in biographies, reference works, and scholarship about historic persons, places, and events. Place names and borders and geography all change over time. Dates are often indeterminate or debates, as in the beginning or ending of a war or transition such as the Industrial Revolution. Many people have no official birth date, or only a year death date, or contradictory data even in Library of Congress or other name authority. Terminology changes, and new concepts of personhood are devised, such that we label the gender expression or sexuality of people in past centuries through our recent understanding—a concern for historians of gay and lesbian cultures for generations. Labels in one language or one cultural context often won't cover phenomena of social life in others. Names, ostensibly the most "proper" of privately owned attributes, are extremely difficult in research contexts: naming practices differ across cultures (surnames first vs. last), and may be translated or transliterated differently by different cataloguers. Women's names are notoriously unstable because of the common practice of changing with marriage. And most people below middle class or beyond imperial powers and language groups have almost no information about them.

Figure 1. Wikidata collects and redistributes demographic label data. When creators produce demographic label data, then either they or others may publish that data in Wikidata. Wikidata itself is a popular source for exporting data for republication elsewhere

2.4.1 Demographic labeling by libraries

With the rise of libraries and of research on human cultures, there have been waves of change in the terminology considered acceptable to designate and sort individuals, objects, events, countries and languages, races, and genders. We discuss these matters here, and report on our further inquiry on gender in name authorities in the Methods section below. In 2018, Lae'l Hughes-Watkins took note of the pressure library catalogues and archives have faced to ensure a "reparative archive" that includes "marginalized voices," in the terms of her article's title. She quotes Ta-Nehisi Coates in his influential article on reparations for slavery and segregation: "the full acceptance of our collective biography and its consequences—is the price we must pay to see ourselves squarely." Linguistic justice is part of a more inclusive history, and those responsible for archival terms take labels seriously as doing potential harm. Take for example the application of gender labels to persons; in the Library of Congress, a record created in 2009 may only have binary terms (male/female), while a record created in 2016 may have a more extensive list to include gender minorities (e.g. transgender individuals). Many individuals and organizations work to continually update the labels that are applied to persons, including one of the most influential controlled vocabularies for catalogue headings, Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH). There are practical reasons to conserve historic headings and add cross-references and additional terms in "see-reference" lists. Individual libraries such as the University of Virginia issue statements on policies to redress the harms of legacy labels such as "illegal aliens" for undocumented immigrants, while necessarily interdependent with the policies and metadata of LCSH.[?] The Library of Congress' policy is to "not respond to requests

to update bibliographic records that were considered correct according to the cataloging standard and level of cataloging used when created.”

Libraries agreed to share a set of MARC (MACHine Readable Catalog) metadata standards since the transition away from card catalogs. Many national libraries along with Wikidata collaborate with the Virtual International Authority File [?]. Library of Congress name authorities are part of a set of records that remained unchanged for nearly 120 years, until several new fields were added to include personal information in 2009. Some fields to be noted are associated group (previously known as affiliation, this includes any association through employment, membership, cultural identity, etc.), occupation, and gender. Prior to this shift in authority work, fields to describe works or persons did not provide contextualization, but were only included to provide enough information for identification and disambiguation. The Library of Congress policy on name authority records is to “not respond to requests to update correct name authority records with additional information.”[]The instability of labels over time becomes increasingly evident in the Library of Congress’ records due to these policies, as the labels do not become updated to reflect the most recent consensus for demographic terms.

2.4.2 Demographic labeling by the US Census Bureau

When the US Census Bureau takes its census every 10 years, it gathers data organized by several different “topics,” including age, sex, race, education level, income, and health insurance coverage. Population-wide statistics for these categories are compiled, calculated, and arranged into tables that are often multidimensional, presenting information on several of these topics at once. These tables can be browsed and downloaded by the general public at this site.

Querying individuals using recently acquired census data is illegal. The bureau has various privacy principles (more extensively defined here), including a promise of confidentiality: “[O]nly a restricted number of authorized people have access to private information and that access is only granted to conduct our work and for no other purposes.” However, personally identifiable information from a US Census is, by law, released to the public after 72 years.

2.4.3 Demographic labeling for advertising, business, media, and monetizing data

It is common commercial practice to advertise to the proper audience for one’s product—even if that audience tends to be from a certain demographic. Thus advertisers, producers of products, and companies selling data, software and systems of communication are motivated to improve demographic targeting, and may be competitively buying the same data. Society knows and accepts this, but may not know how this data is being used. Private companies often offer sets of the data they have accumulated for academic or advertising purposes, usually by having interested parties apply to gain access to an API. Note that this data is thus not fully open, as it requires an application procedure and vetting process for access.

In the midst of the profound debates and dilemmas regarding the politics and meanings of terms of identity, there is personal data of “sensitive” nature, as the *New York Times* knows. The current online Privacy Policy of that newspaper of record addresses concerns about what the paper will do with subscribers’ data (“What Are Your Rights?”). Regarding “sensitive personal information,” the policy begins, “We generally don’t want to gather any sensitive information about you,” and they pointedly reject being given the kinds of data on a bulleted list; readers should not give the Times: “Your social security number/ Your racial or ethnic origin/ Your political opinions/ Your religion or other beliefs/ Your health, biometric or genetic characteristics/ Any trade union membership/ Any criminal background.” [?] Most readers today likely agree on the sensitivity of these kinds of information—they might have different lists, but concur on the right to privacy.

Meta—the conglomerate that runs Facebook—holds data on its enormous userbase. As of the first quarter of 2022, Facebook has about 2.93 billion monthly users.⁹ The company provides various

⁹<https://www.statista.com/statistics/264810/number-of-monthly-active-facebook-users-worldwide/>

data sets for academic researchers. One must apply to receive access to this data. Most of this data evades demographic information on Facebook users. Indeed, one source for this semi-publicly available Facebook data, CrowdTangle, explicitly mentions “demographic information on users” as what it “doesn’t track.” On the other hand, another source of this data, Ad Library, includes “demographic information (age and gender)” among the data you might be able to access from it. Facebook regularly uses data gleaned from their users’ behaviors to create lists of their interests, which are in turn used for targeting them in advertisement. As Hitlin et al show, roughly half (51%) of all Facebook users are uncomfortable with having their data used to create these lists, though 59% of them admit that the list accurately reflects their interests.¹⁰

Most publicly, Facebook was criticized over its data’s usage for political advertising by the British firm Cambridge Analytica.¹¹ In a report from the Pew Research Center, 74% of users reported not knowing that a list of their interests and traits were being tracked, despite being able to access this information on their account. This information can be used by advertisers to target advertisements to certain demographic groups. A 2016 ProPublica report showed that Facebook allowed advertisers to exclude or target ethnic groups in their audience. Facebook overturned the practice a few years later, but a report by the Markup showed how advertisers could continue to target their ads via proxies for demographics, such as an interest in a particular minority’s culture.¹²¹³ In 2016, a controversy surrounding racially biased housing, employment, and credit advertisements prompted a change in the company’s policies. While a discussion of the ethics of targeted advertising by demographics is outside the scope of this paper, it is important to consider how an open data environment may change the current standard.

Like many other companies, Twitter allows for targeted advertising on its platform, which can target based on demographic features, like gender, language, and location. Even if this information is not freely given by users, Twitter may still analyze other factors to arrive at an estimate (for instance: “We use the gender provided by people in their profiles, and extend that data to other people based on factors of account likeness to determine the gender of people haven’t manually entered their preferred gender.”).

2.4.4 Demographic labeling in academia

Based on informal interviews and emails with respective staff at the University of Virginia, higher education institutions gather demographic information about their employees including tenured faculty but strive to control use of that information for internal purposes such as targeted communications about retirement benefits or statistics for meeting stated diversity goals, or for reporting to accrediting agencies. Metrics of scholarly production, citation indexes, are a coveted commodity. Often personal pages on departmental websites are controlled for consistent format but are voluntarily filled out by the subject, author of their own public profile or searchable CV. For decades initiatives to identify pay and promotion inequities have assembled institution-wide data (at state institutions, salaries are required to be public), as also by non-profit organizations monitoring education. Nevertheless, demographic analysis of living persons can be prohibited, much like census data. See: <https://www.rsc.org/new-perspectives/talent/joint-commitment-for-action-inclusion-and-diversity-in-publishing/progress-so-far> ; this person had a Wikidata project to catalog Dutch professors in 2019 <https://nl.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gebruiker:Sjoerddebruin>; he had to only catalog dead ones.

Inspired by initial investigations into the existence of implicit bias in journal publishing, various publishers in the sciences have recently committed themselves to tracking racial demographics among their authors. This demographic data is generally acquired through self-reporting via surveys. Leading a group of 52 publishing organizations, the Royal Society of Chemistry describes its goal in

¹⁰<https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2019/01/16/facebook-algorithms-and-personal-data/> - this is on zotero

¹¹<https://www.businessinsider.com/cambridge-analytica-whistleblower-christopher-wylie-facebook-data-2019-10>

¹²<https://www.propublica.org/article/facebook-lets-advertisers-exclude-users-by-race?token=XHXNgmPVImDaW15WrSaCeUz9xwCZGa7E>

¹³<https://themarkup.org/citizen-browser/2021/07/09/facebook-got-rid-of-racial-ad-categories-or-did-it>

acquiring researchers' demographic information as "understanding its research community" to "reduc[e] bias in [its] own publishing activities."

Nickoal Eichmann-Kalward, Jeana Jorgensen, and Scott B. Weingart have studied "fifteen years of D[igital] H[umanities] conferences" specifically "to call out the biases and lack of diversity" and "to show that simplistic, reductive quantitative methods can be applied critically, and need not feed into techno-utopic fantasies" or claims of "a direct line to Truth" ("Representation at Digital Humanities Conferences (2000-2015)," *Bodies of Information* 73). They find "a large gender gap," and a lack of "non-English names" in peer review. "We could not get data on ethnicity, race, or skin color" but draw on "regional and name data" to infer that such diversity is low (73-4). The work can be accessed at <https://dh-abstracts.library.cmu.edu/> Bob Ducharme has shown how it can be turned into RDF: <https://www.bobdc.com/blog/dhconfrdfpart1/>

2.4.5 Demographic labeling in the Wikimedia platform

ORCID grantmaking foundations United States government

3 Methods

3.1 Researching Aspects of Library Labeling: Name Authority Records with New Attributes: Gender

How do libraries approach demographic labeling? The addition of new entity attribute fields in 2009 such as gender, occupation, and affiliated group has introduced demographic labeling as a relatively new subject in cataloging. Some individuals argue for simplicity; believing authority records should only provide enough information for disambiguation. Others, including librarians at the University of Virginia, cite issues with cataloging inconsistencies; labels applied to a name authority record vary across libraries based on staff and resource availability. A smaller staff will only have the resources to apply more basic fields to authority records (Whitney Buccicone, head of technical services for Special Collections at the University of Virginia). Regardless of differing opinions on labeling in libraries, the Name Authority Cooperative Program (NACO), a part of the Library of Congress Program for Cooperative Cataloging (PCC), outlines how to apply these labels in its Participants' Manual.

Once records have been created and published to the Library of Congress linked data service, the Library of Congress Name Authority Files (LCNAF) database is reconciled against other datasets including Wikidata. The linked data environment allows a biographical profile created by the record to circulate openly for use and reuse. Name Authority Files are available for public download from the Library of Congress' linked data service. Once downloaded, SPARQL can be used to query the data. Querying Entity Attributes can return results for a demographic label, such as associated group, occupation, or gender (MARC fields 373, 374, or 375).

Authority records limit core elements, and exclude gender, occupation, affiliated group, and other 3XX fields from the list of core RDA (Research Description and Access) elements; they are optional, hence the inconsistencies in their application. NACO encourages the inclusion of these fields *when available* "because such information can be especially helpful for disambiguating like or similar entities and for creating unique, descriptive name identifiers" (Participants' Manual, 2020). *So when should identification labeling, if available, be applied?* More labeling seems to have its benefits. This is a question that is central to the practice of demographic labeling, and one that can be discussed in the context of field 375, gender.

Gender as a label in name authority records has been the source of extensive discussion and controversy. Mirroring the evolution of society's application of gender terms, the field has populated many changes since its initial introduction in 2009. When created, the Library of Congress intended for the inclusion of gender in name authority records to provide means of disambiguation, contextualization, and facilitation of gender-specific searches (e.g. in an effort to sort by female authors). At this time, catalogers were instructed to choose primarily from the following list of terms: male,

female, or unknown. The binary labels were not representative of more modern terms of gender expression, leading to the field being updated in 2016. A report from the PCC Ad Hoc Task Group proposed to extend accepted terms to include gender minorities, intersex, transgender, and transsexuals. By 2020, the NACO Participants Manual had grown to include ten best practices for applying gender to a record, which was more extensive than any other field. Some of these best practices included: “record information about gender as the person self-identifies and explicitly discloses”; “Do not assume gender identity based on pictures or names”; record terms “in accordance with the term used by the person.” The overarching recommendation in the manual advised catalogers to “exercise restraint in adding gender terms to authority records.” Finally, the most recent (April 2022) recommendation from the PCC Ad Hoc Task Group has led the Library of Congress to remove the field entirely.

3.2 Exploration of Wikipedia and Wikidata

The expansion and retraction of terms in the library and archive community to designate different personal attributes is instructive for the benefits and harms of labeling. As most people in the world do not begin their queries about people by searching an online library catalog, we focus instead on Wikipedia and Wikidata to understand the ethics surrounding real-life practices of demographic labeling on open datasets. Without attempting exhaustive studies of Wikipedia (nearly seven million articles in English) or Wikidata (over 98 million data items), we have indicated that the standards for labeling are interconnected: Wikidata participates in VIAF, and a user of Wikipedia encounters Library of Congress subject headings and data about persons in citations. Any Wikidata entry can be accessed on its corresponding Wikipedia page via a link in the left hand column of the Wikipedia article. Wikidata contains an entire portal concerning the integration of Wikipedia into Wikidata, foregrounded near its main help page.

Just as archivists and librarians have sought to revise pejorative subject headings and to serve equity and inclusion in name authority practices, online data communities tread carefully around certain especially controversial labels: race/ethnicity, religion, gender, and sexual orientation. Within Wikipedia and Wikidata, we look at several case studies as representative examples of how the Wiki community engages with labeling. We look at an example Wikipedia bot—a software program that automatically performs tasks—to see how Wiki contributors place restrictions that consider demographic labeling. We also perform queries on demographic labels ourselves, showcasing Wikidata’s openness and the potentially controversial hazards surrounding it.

3.3 WikiProject Biography - Human Model

As part of WikiProject Biography, our team has constructed a “model” for the “human being,” that is, a structured and organized (partial) list of characteristics that Wikidata can—and in most cases does—fill in for persons on its database. In part, the model displays the sheer number of qualities upon which a human being might be queried on Wikidata. These range from the seemingly anodyne (“eye color”) to the potentially invasive/controversial (“religion or worldview,” “convicted of,” “medical condition”), to the bizarre (“possessed by spirit”).

In addition to these qualitative features, Wikidata entries also include information about the presence of subjects on external websites and sources. Various account names—for example, Twitter, Reddit, and TikTok—are attached to people where possible. Additionally, a significant amount of “identifiers” are attached to many Wikidata entries—these are links to persons’ entries on other databases. Thus Wikidata sits as the central node or repository of the various networks in which people tend to be enmeshed.

This model not only shows the range of qualities upon which human beings are already categorized and query-able, but serves to show the criteria on which a totalizing model of the human being can be constructed. Much (all?) of this information is gleaned or derived from publicly available databases, and by grouping it all together on Wikidata, querying individuals or populations

is easy and quick. Wikidata's coalescence of disparate databases particularly facilitates intersectional queries: one could, to construct a representative example, find Twitter account names for all African-American women in Wikidata's database born after 1980, with at least 3 children, who espouse some kind of left-wing political ideology and were educated at an Ivy League school. Such granularity of detail, impossible on more focused databases, is a direct result of Wikidata's omnivorous collection of data. Queries below display similar sorts of intersectional identities in SPARQL.

3.4 Wikidata queries to showcase data holdings

Rather than use Wikidata's dedicated query webpage, we wrote our queries with a Jupyter notebook. This method allowed us to more easily export data to a CSV file and share both the code and its output with other researchers via GitHub. Wikidata queries use SPARQL: a language built for databases that adhere to the Resource Description Framework (RDF) standard. RDF structures data in "triples," with each triple consisting of a subject, predicate, and object. Per Wikipedia, "the subject denotes the resource, and the predicate denotes traits or aspects of the resource, and expresses a relationship between the subject and the object." So for the phrase "the cat lives in Charlottesville," "the cat" is the subject, "lives in" is the predicate, and "Charlottesville" is the object. RDF places no limits on the number of triples associated with a given entity, allowing for a given Wikidata table about an entity to be as complete as its sources allow. Again, we should ask if the proliferation of inter-operable attributes is a benefit—better representation of diversity and individuality—or a reinforcement of differences that support inequality. Further, having more information out there about oneself can be harmful in minor and major ways.

4 Results

4.1 Demographic labeling in Wikipedia articles

Like other encyclopedic sources, Wikipedia articles vary within certain parameters—expected information items in a certain form and sequence. The interface gives the impression that articles are written by one anonymous, collective voice; rather than bylines, the version history of an article can indicate the Wikipedia identities of contributors. A Manual of Style for Wikimedians insists that "verifiable content is more important than formatting," but also sets parameters that will meet approval by other editors and guide readers to easily access the information they seek.[?]] As in many newspaper and encyclopedia articles, a page about a person will have a "lead section" that summarizes the significance of the person's life, followed by sections and subsections. (Note that many feature interview/profiles or biographies in print prefer to begin by narrating a scene in the individual's life.) For display, each page has an infobox (right side of browser) and a table of contents (left side, below lead). Labeling or aspects of identity considered attributes by NACO can be found in all parts of an article about a person, but especially in the lead section, especially its opening lines, as well as the infobox, and sections with titles such as "early life and education," "family life" or "death."

See, for instance, the introduction of Anne Frank's Wikipedia article:

Annelies Marie Frank (12 June 1929 – c. February 1945) was a German-Dutch diarist of Jewish heritage. One of the most discussed Jewish victims of the Holocaust, she gained fame posthumously with the 1947 publication of *The Diary of a Young Girl*...

This example contains several identifying labels, beginning with the standard modern signifiers of unique personhood: legal name and known dates of birth and death. Quickly, the specific significance of this person takes shape with other stated attributes in this lead section: nationality, religious background, occupation (Frank's gender is also indicated with the use of female pronoun). Demographic labeling may also occur throughout the rest of the article's main text, but demographic labeling within the lead section is often given heightened consideration due to its primacy of position. In this case, a well-documented, renowned life can be subject to continuing debate, as indicated by the subsection "Denials of authenticity and legal action" (controversies about lack of evidence sparked

by Holocaust deniers). Notability is enhanced all the more by controversies related to world crises, as indicated in this instance by the note that pops up if one tries to edit the page: "This page is semi-protected so that only autoconfirmed users can edit it." Anne Frank's representative status as author of the famous *Diary* raises ethical issues, and at one time to reveal her identity in Amsterdam was deadly. Wikipedia's process tries to protect a consensus on documented truths about this distinctive writer's cultural background and experience.

Like many Wikipedia articles on individuals, Frank's page also features an infobox holding other pieces of demographic data: languages spoken, education and institutions attended, and birth and death locations. References and bibliography in a biographical entry may aid in constructing an extensive set of demographic attributes. After these listings, one can show the Name Authority record, with links to external sources, including International Standard Name Identifier and VIAF. Finally, a list of categories that Frank falls into can be found in a box at the bottom of her article, such as "stateless people"; many of these terms in effect apply more than one demographic label. Potentially, there is more responsible and responsive recognition of a person if the identifying attributes, or the kinds of information collected, such as family life, hobbies or tastes, etc., are included—the less abstract or yes/no sorting, the more justice. But possibly, the less privacy.

4.1.1 Wikipedia tracks its edits and offers a discussion forum on each page

Voluntary, and in part driven by current events and controversies, the editing of Wikipedia has instant impact but is actually incremental, far from the goal of complete repository of knowledge. All edits on Wikipedia, even those made by non-human programs, are tracked in a publicly-accessible log. This log is found by clicking on the "View history" tab at the top of the page. Editors of Wikipedia are asked to submit an "edit summary," a brief description of the changes they have made. Including an edit summary is, however, optional, which can make it difficult to ascertain the motivation behind an edit.

If extensive discussion of a page's contents is warranted, editors might discuss it on the page's discussion forum, found under the "Talk" tab at the top of the page. Here, editors propose topics and respond to topics raised by others; the talks tend to concern some controversial aspect of the page's text. Demographic labels are frequently discussed at length on talk pages. The Wikimedia community cares to be accurate and respectful of sensitive personal data.

4.2 Bots make data more accessible

The use of bots is an essential part of the Wikipedia editorial community's process reviewing and maintaining content in Wikipedia. Bots are software programs that automatically look through and process Wikipedia articles for various tasks necessary to the maintenance of Wikipedia. Bots do many things, including fixing redirect links, countering vandalism, and recommending tasks to editors.

There are some restrictions placed on bot functions due to ethical considerations. For example, Wikipedia policy dictates that bots are not supposed to place people into categories. The policy stands with an eye towards sensitive categories. For their likelihood of sparking controversy, the four categories of gender, race/ethnicity, sexuality, and religion, are consistently singled out for various reasons on Wikipedia.

On the other hand, there seem to be fewer restrictions placed on bots that convert information already on Wikipedia into structured data on Wikidata. A bot named Emijrpbot 6 scans new Wikipedia biographies, populating their Wikidata entries for gender if the field is empty. It's worth looking into precisely what heuristic Emijrpbot 6 uses to assign gender. A look at the source code shows that gender assignment follows several steps. Translated into plain English, the bot first checks if the new page is assigned to any gendered categories (i.e. any category with the words "male/female," "men/women," or uses occupational terms like "actor/actress"). Beyond that, a basic semantic formula is applied, which can be divided into two calculations:

1. If the page is under 2000 characters long: Does it include at least one example from the most common set of gender pronouns (he/his/him or she/her/hers), without including at least one example of the pronouns from the other side of the binary?
2. If the page is over 2000 characters long: Does one set of gender pronouns appear at least twice on the page, and at least three times as often as the pronouns from the other side of the binary?

The Wikipedia community has accepted this as a formula for algorithmically determining the gender of the subjects of biographies for the purpose of creating gender labels in the corresponding Wikidata records.

In addition to calculating gender, the bot also attempts to add occupation data for individuals on Wikidata. It does this by sifting through the individual's Wikipedia page's categories. The bot also strips category names to determine birth and death dates. The bot takes advantage of the fact that category names follow a fairly standardized template and can thus be easily manipulated through Python regular expressions (e.g. Joe Biden's categories include "1942 births," "Public defenders," and "Delaware lawyers").

The bot performs several overall checks before augmenting Wikidata for the person: it ensures that the person under consideration is of type "human" in Wikidata; it ensures that the Wikipedia page is in fact classed as a biography; and it does not add information if the Wikipedia page has the words "murder" or "disappearance" in its title. All of these help the bot avoid controversial or inappropriate data transfer.

4.3 Wikidata queries make public data even more accessible

Wikipedia and Wikidata are purposefully accessible to the public—more is always more, we should because we can. The user search or the designed query can easily gather heaps of personal information, whether sensitive and involuntary or authorized by the subjects. Thus, Wikidata can be the foundation of demographic querying, the retrieval of information about individuals based on searches (digital or otherwise) on these demographic labels within sets of data containing them. Unforeseen interconnections of multiple data points may introduce violations of privacy or consequences similar to the harms of social media.

Our demographic queries in this project occupy an ethical spectrum ranging from less to more objectionable. Wikidata amasses information on millions of people from numerous public datasets; at this scale it is impossible to imagine a query that nobody would find invasive or at least uncomfortable. Thus, at one end of our spectrum we queried demographic information most likely to be viewed as benign. Data that circulates on a mass, global scale likely fits this criteria, so we selected Olympian athletes as our first group of individuals. Wikidata sources athletes' information in part from the International Olympic Committee's website, and we limited our categories to those present in that dataset: name, sex or gender, and sport. Since competitors are aware of their information being collected and broadcast by the IOC, other sports organizations, and media outlets, we imagine many would not object to their information being present in our query results. Again, though, the sheer number of Olympians in the past century raises the probability that some would be uncomfortable with this dataset.

Opposite Olympians on the ethical spectrum, our second query focuses on people with a health condition categorized as a sexually-transmitted infection (STI). Health information constitutes some of a person's most private data, and though that heightened sensitivity limits the category's footprint on Wikidata, it remains an apt example of information many people would find invasive or otherwise objectionable. At first we explored the possibility of analyzing individuals with any health condition, but we soon decided to focus our query further. Since sexual health conditions are often viewed as an even more private matter than those affecting other biological systems, they seemed suitable for our purposes. Alongside information on people's health condition(s), we included sex or gender or cause of death if known. Again, the ethical sensitivity is greater for the living than the dead.

Finally, and most directly relevant to Scholia, we queried Wikidata for demographic information on past and present employees of University of Virginia. Wikidata lacks data on many aspects of an individual's time at UVA, so we were unable to query for an employee's years of employment, profession, or organizational position. However, we queried many of the demographic categories discussed in this paper: sex or gender, ethnicity, birthplace, citizenship, religion, and sexuality. Despite many of these categories having minimal data—with only one person having a value for sexuality—they provide a foundation for more revealing scholarly profiles as Wikidata's entries become more complete.

4.4 PUT TANNER'S QUERIES HERE

Sex or Gender	Citizenship	Sport
10,814 female	29,100 data available	29,406 data available
18,751 male	551 data unavailable	165 data unavailable
1 intersex		
1 non-binary		
2 transgender female		
2 transgender male		

Table 2. Olympian query

Sex or Gender	Citizenship	Condition	Cause of Death
141 male	143 data available	143 HIV/AIDS	117 AIDS-related complications
10 female	11 data unavailable	2 gonorrhea	21 other
1 genderfluid		11 syphilis	17 data unavailable
1 transgender female			
1 data unavailable			

Table 3. STI query

Sex or Gender	Citizenship	Religion	Sexuality	Ethnicity
831 male	471 data available	19 data available	1 homosexuality	10 data available
267 female	1,224 data unavailable	1,676 data unavailable	1,694 data unavailable	1,685 data unavailable
597 data unavailable				

Table 4. University of Virginia query

5 Discussion

5.1 Demographic labeling in the Wikimedia platform

5.1.1 The nature of the platform includes applying labels

5.1.2 Accelerating rate of transfer between prose and datasets

Wikidata shares Wikipedia's commitment to neutrality. As a representative example, consider the guidelines for Wikidata "descriptions" (the "short phrases designed to disambiguate" items on the project), which dictate avoiding "opinionated, biased, or promotional wording" and "controversial claims." The potentially sensitive/privacy-invasive labels listed above are consistently acknowledged as requiring care on Wikidata: see, for instance, the entry on the sexual orientation property, which

directs editors to “use IF AND ONLY IF they have stated it themselves, unambiguously, or it has been widely agreed upon by historians after their death,” or the entry on the ethnic group property, which states, “a VERY high standard of proof is needed . . . 1) the subject claims it themselves, or 2) it is widely agreed on by scholars, or 3) is fictional and portrayed as such.”

Community discussion of the integration of Wikipedia and the Wikidata resources has various fronts and is partly summarized in this essay. Discussions about their integration often provide intriguing test cases for standards on the two websites. For example, a 2013 discussion yielded the policy that Wikidata could be invoked to populate infoboxes on Wikipedia pages, but not to automatically populate the main text of the article: such a standard shows the more general care afforded to article main texts over infoboxes. On the other hand, a more recent effort seeks to establish a system of citing Wikidata as a reliable source for Wikipedia articles, suggesting that Wikidata might be used as a source of information.

Transferring any information on Wikipedia to the more highly structured data formats of Wikidata may be an especially ethically charged task, due to Wikidata’s centrality in the linked open data cloud. Amazon’s Alexa and Apple’s Siri, for instance, use Wikidata for various functions. Wikidata itself acknowledges that some of its categories may violate privacy. Though Wikipedia is mindful of demographic labeling of people, especially when it comes to sensitive categories, the importation of those categories’ inherent information to Wikidata seems not to be as assiduously regulated.

5.2 Wikipedia’s established discourse on demographic labels

There has been popular off-wiki discussion about Wikipedia’s application of demographic labels since at least 2013. On Wikipedia itself, ethical standards around demographic labels are particularly defined for living persons. Wikipedia carefully balances living persons’ privacy with its general inclusion of relevant information from reliable sources.

Wikipedia’s editorial community has rules about the application of demographic labels. These rules are particularly careful when applied to biographies of living persons (BLP). The prevailing considerations are principles important to Wikipedia at large: namely, neutral point of view and usage of reliable sources. When material on living persons is added to Wikipedia that violates these principles, it is “removed immediately and without waiting for discussion.” Restraint is favored over sensationalism: as its guideline page suggests, BLPs “must be written conservatively and with regard for the subject’s privacy.”

The decision of applying a particular demographic label onto an individual on Wikipedia can sometimes be the source of debate. Discussions of demographic labeling can be found on articles’ talk pages, though in certain circumstances, the main article itself will address or reproduce this discussion. Decisions tend to be done on a case-by-case basis. Some aspects of demographic labeling are laid out in Wikipedia’s Manual of Style. However, a few considerations are consistently taken into account when deciding the appropriateness of various labels.

5.2.1 Individual Preferences

In general, Wikipedia articles respect individual preference in cases of disputed demographic profiling.

For instance, the Wikipedia article on the author Philip Roth respects his preference to not be labeled as “Jewish-American.” Though Jewish-American identity was indisputably a major theme of Roth’s fiction, he rejected his labeling as such on grounds of his secularism. In the community discussion on Roth, these competing claims are laid out, the final word (which the article’s language reflects) explicitly referring to what Roth “preferred.”

Applying demographic labels to trans and nonbinary persons Gender identity, in particular, can lead to extensive discussions of demographic labeling on Wikipedia, especially the appropriate naming and pronoun usage for individuals who identify as trans, non-binary, or gender-non-conforming. As an example, one might examine a

The film's directors, Lana and Lilly Wachowski, are trans women who, when directing *The Matrix* in the late 1990s, presented as men, and indeed are credited for the film under their (gendered) former stage name, The Wachowski Brothers.

Labeling dead people/retroactive demographic labeling Complications arise when assigning certain demographic labels to individuals who died without specifying their preferences. Individuals may be given demographic labels that did not exist or were not in wide usage during their lifetime. The Wikipedia article for Civil Rights activist Pauli Murray, who has retroactively been classified as trans or gender-non-conforming despite living before widespread usage of these identities, features discussions of Murray's gender identity on both its talk page and its main page. These discussions do not arrive at a final conclusion; indeed, the inconclusiveness of the discussions appears to be the rationale for including an exposition of them on the article's main page.

Rejecting individual preference In certain cases, an individual's preferences for demographic labeling may be rejected. To take a famous example, the Wikipedia article for Rachel Dolezal does not refer to her as Black (nor is she included in any categories for Black people or African Americans), even though she has identified as Black for many years.

Rejecting individual preferences often occurs when describing people with contentious labels—descriptors like “racist”, “transphobic”, or “terrorist”—is singled out early in Wikipedia's guide for tone in biographies of living persons: “Do not label people with contentious labels, loaded language, or terms that lack precision, unless a person is commonly described that way in reliable sources.” On occasion, living persons request their own articles to be deleted, but this is generally denied.

5.2.2 Due weight

What are the primary grounds for this individual's notability? The Wikipedia principle of due weight, part of its more general principle of maintaining a neutral point of view, holds that articles ought to cover competing viewpoints based on their respective representation in the population, with very minority viewpoints receiving little to no coverage at all. Wikipedia seeks to “balance aspects,” that is, to “not give undue weight to minor aspects of [a] subject but should strive to treat each aspect with a weight proportional to its treatment in the body of reliable, published material on the subject.” With regards to the demographic labeling of individuals, undue weight may be brought into consideration when some demographic aspect of an individual receives over-representation at the expense of their other demographic aspects.

Due weight came into consideration on the Wikipedia article for Michael Sam, an American football player who achieved significant success at the collegiate level but is now almost exclusively known for being the first openly gay player to be selected in the NFL draft. His article's talk page shows an example of the discussion of due weight with regards to demographic labeling; his lead section mentions his sexuality only briefly.

5.2.3 Sorting into categories is given particular ethical consideration

The sorting of living persons into categories is given special care because categories “do not carry disclaimers or modifiers”; therefore, category names must be “made clear by the article text and its reliable sources.” The Wiki community has designated some demographic categories as “properties that may violate privacy,” which include (but are not limited to): gender identity, nationality, race, ethnicity, religion, sexuality, marital status, education level, class or income level, occupation, and age.

In addition to these sensitive demographic groupings, caution is particularly given to categorizations that might attach negative connotations to the subject. For instance, the classing of persons into categories signifying criminal status is singled out as requiring extra caution: “Category:Criminals and its subcategories should be added only for an incident that is relevant to the person's notability; the incident was published by reliable third-party sources; the subject was convicted; and the conviction was not overturned on appeal. In particular, do not categorize biographies of living people

under such contentious topics as racism, sexism, extremism. . .”

All of these rules on categorization extend more generally to other forms of sorting and classing individuals on Wikipedia (e.g. infoboxes, lists, and navigation templates).

5.3 Support and opposition for demographic labeling

The practice of categorizing persons by gender, race, or other labels can be a necessary step for promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion. Institutions can wield consistent and accurate demographic labeling to achieve various kinds of demographic representation. At the same time, such labels discriminate, and may be tools of discrimination. When personal information is automatically extracted and labeled, we see the threats to privacy; the visibly identified person is subjected to potential misinterpretation or misuse of that information.

Any agency (governmental, corporate, educational) using the data may be guided by an ethics of care or instead by surveillance and behavioral control, and many purposes in between. Scholarship and non-profit information resources are not exempt from the dangers of pinning and sorting persons in data categories. We start from the awareness that demographic labeling’s utility cannot be evaluated without considering the privacy and sensitivity of personal data.

Our approach to demographic labeling in Wikimedia’s data is guided by awareness of the controversial history of discourses of identification, in the context of encyclopedic or quantitative approaches to national and international records of people. Quick precis of what we decided to do in this paper.

5.3.1 Should we do it, just because we can?

Personal data privacy has already galloped far away from the barn. All kinds of automated data collection, far less voluntary than subscribing to a newspaper, have built discrimination and legal action into the mix. In July, 2022, many women in the United States are concerned to remove geo-tracking and menstrual tracking apps from their smartphones because of changing laws that might end in asking someone who has crossed state lines or who has missed periods to account for not having a child. We share in the widespread motivation to add missing elements in the world’s history, through initiatives such as editing biographical pages for the 1000 Women in Religion WikiProject [?] or compiling lists of women in various fields [?]. But at what point does the modifier "female" become less than inclusive and more disqualifying for the main prize? We would not want to return to specifying the woman doctor or doctress when men are just plain doctor. Sorting people into either of two sexes has raised objections in feminist and gender theory; it is deemed essentialist, another way of saying it presumes that biology determines culture. Postcolonial theorist Gayatri Spivak influentially noted a need for "strategic essentialism" in advocating independence and rights for colonized peoples [?], but has warned against uncritical, reductive group identification in nationalism. Édouard Glissant posits the idea of a right to opacity, a protection of the alterity of a person from the systemic systems of knowledge and world power; even the social science or government of the colonizer cannot invade that space.[? ?] The philosopher Judith Butler influentially challenged the idea of innate gender or binary sexual identity. [?] The rise of queer theory at the end of the twentieth century increasingly critiqued essentialism and explored the construction of identities by cultural discourses of difference that supported norms such as whiteness and heterosexual masculinity. Influenced by queer theory and LGBTQ+ movements, the very term "woman" has been challenged, as it hardly keeps up with the complexity of understanding of gender today. In machine learning contexts, researchers seek ways to predict gender or race for various purposes such as ensuring equity in peer review or health care managing the documented risks that vary by race. Benthall and Haynes (2019), “Racial Categories in Machine Learning,” propose an alternative to the stark choices, to “be blind to racial group disparities and thereby reify racialized social inequality by no longer measuring systemic inequality, or be conscious of racial categories in a way that itself reifies race.” Instead, they write of a third alternative: “with unsupervised learning to dynamically detect patterns of segregation, machine learning systems can mitigate the root cause of social disparities, social segregation and stratification, without further anchoring status categories

of disadvantage.” It often appears that questions of diversity, equity, and inclusion are overlaid on pre-existing structured systems that have built in bias in data collection, metadata, and algorithmic models. Critical questioning of categories should where possible engage every level in the stack, every phase of scholarship, but modularity may allow intervention at later stages (see Alan Liu, “Diversity Stack”).

- We note a fundamental divide in the question of the ethics of collecting and using data about personal attributes: the “say” of the living vs. the dead. A remove from living descendants diminishes concern about revealing. Are we only researching the living?
- Scholarly citations of software, by definition, are probably identifying living people.
- Narrative biography about a person is always biased or incomplete but may feel more adequate for recognition of the unique person. Any recognition is framed by the social consensus on performed roles such as parent, politician, ski jumper. New conceptions of the systems of recognition can take shape with the massive data collected in Wikidata, to reduce the prescription of what people can occupy those roles.

5.3.2 Reasons for support

In general, the primary reason for supporting and practicing demographic labeling is the desire to provide accurate information about people and, as just stated, to help alter prejudices about overlapping attributes, such as female surfer, straight male fashion designer, Black astronaut. Through robust demographic labeling, one can develop a strong profile of an individual, perhaps useful for individuals in the public eye. By keeping this data structured (as on, for example, Wikipedia), one can easily perform demographic queries on individuals and populations. Querying populations on the basis of demographic labels can help identify trends of disproportionate representation. To redress inequities, it can be necessary to identify the grounds of discrimination first.

5.3.3 Reasons against

On the other hand, demographic labeling proves controversial primarily on the grounds of privacy. Various properties are more likely than others to violate privacy: race/ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, and religion and the most commonly cited ones. Certain demographic labels might also serve to overshadow other parts of a person’s life and work, or slot people into groups at the expense of highlighting their individual experiences.

5.4 Directions for further exploration

Will we have an ethical dilemma or a practical recommendation? Is it open season on all personal data? Nature is wishy-washy on how much they can do to track? They are going to monetize the data. More study needed. Snapshot of what is done now. Community is going to develop its own standards.

6 Conclusions

Ethical guidelines for representation of individuals meet incompatible values: 1) additional specific data is more true to the individual, less reductive; 2) additional data is likely to be more intrusive, especially in sensitive areas a violation of the right to privacy. More information amplifies, but it may reinforce the label as if essential or natural. Perhaps even more data, on the global scale the Wikidata approaches, can help document systems of recognition we will agree to change. It may also, with due skepticism and further research like this project, begin to break down the illusion of a-historical objectivity in all of our labels. A collaboration between bots and humans, a massive database of attributes for human beings, may strive to avoid the erosion of the right to privacy and put such a right in historical perspective. A collaborative resource that anyone can edit can also be a sandbox for revising the way we label persons.

7 References

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